

A Comparative Study of Outcome of Flipped Classroom Assisted Lecture Classes and Traditional Lecture Classes among First-Year MBBS Students in a Medical College

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Abstract:

Background: In medical education, teaching methodologies play a vital part in student learning and academic performance. The flipped classroom model, which includes students dealing with lecture content outside of class as well as using class time for interactive activities, has gained attention as a potential alternative to traditional lecture-based instruction.

Aim: To evaluate and compare the efficiency of flipped classroom methodology versus traditional lecture-based classes on the academics and engagement of first-year MBBS students in a medical college.

Methods: This comparative study evaluated the outcomes of flipped classroom-assisted versus traditional lecture classes among 130 first-year MBBS students of two academic sessions at E.S.I.C.M.C.H., Bihta, Patna. Students were randomly assigned to either the flipped or traditional classroom group, with both groups covering the same curriculum and assessed using pre-tests and post-tests.

Results: The study involved 130 first-year MBBS students, with 65 in each group. Both groups had similar pre-test scores, but after 10 months, the flipped classroom group showed significantly higher post-test scores (75.6 vs. 68.4, $p < 0.001$) and greater improvement in scores (18.5 vs. 12.1, $p < 0.001$). Student feedback indicated higher engagement, understanding, enjoyment, and overall approval with the flipped classroom method compared to traditional lectures.

Conclusion: The flipped classroom model was found to be more effective than traditional lectures in enhancing academic performance and student engagement among first-year MBBS students. This method provides a more interactive and student-centred learning experience, leading to better educational outcomes.

Recommendations: Based on the findings, it is recommended that medical colleges consider integrating flipped classroom techniques into their curricula to improve student learning and engagement. Further research with larger sample sizes and diverse educational settings is needed to validate these results and explore long-term impacts.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom, Traditional Lectures, Medical Education, Student Engagement, Academic Performance.

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Introduction

Medical education has evolved significantly over the years, increasingly incorporating innovative teaching methods to improve student learning outcomes. One such method, the flipped classroom model, has gained recognition as an effective alternative to traditional lecture-based instruction. Unlike conventional lectures, where students passively receive information, the flipped classroom approach promotes active learning by requiring students to review lecture materials outside of class and participate in interactive

activities during class time. This pedagogical shift aims to create a more dynamic and student-centred learning environment, which is especially important in medical education, where a deep understanding and practical application of knowledge are essential [1].

Traditional lecture-based instruction has been the cornerstone of medical education for decades, providing a structured format where instructors deliver content in a one-way communication style. While effective in disseminating information, this

approach often falls short in addressing individual learning needs and promoting deeper understanding. The passive nature of traditional lectures can limit student engagement and reduce opportunities for practical application of knowledge. As medical curricula become increasingly complex, there is a growing need to explore alternative teaching methods that can better meet the demands of both students and educators [2].

The flipped classroom model, by contrast, redefines the role of classroom time and homework. Students are required to engage with instructional materials, such as video lectures or readings, at home before class. This preparatory work allows class time to be utilized for active learning activities, including discussions, problem-solving exercises, and peer collaborations. The aim of this method is to enhance student comprehension and retention of material through more interactive and applied learning experiences. In medical education, where critical thinking and clinical application are essential, the flipped classroom could potentially offer significant advantages over traditional methods [3,4].

Despite the growing adoption of the flipped classroom approach, there remains a need for empirical evidence to validate its effectiveness, especially in the context of medical education. This study seeks to address this gap by comparing the outcomes of flipped classroom-assisted lecture classes with traditional lecture classes among first-year MBBS students. By examining both academic performance and student engagement, this research aims to provide insights into the relative efficacy of these teaching methodologies. The results of this study could inform future curriculum design and pedagogical strategies in medical schools.

The aim of this study is to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of the flipped classroom methodology against traditional lecture-based classes in terms of academic performance and student engagement among first-year MBBS students. Through this comparative analysis, the study seeks to determine whether the flipped classroom approach can offer substantial benefits over traditional methods, thereby contributing to the ongoing improvement of medical education practices.

Methodology

Study Design: This was a comparative study designed to evaluate the outcomes of flipped classroom-assisted lecture classes versus traditional lecture classes among first-year MBBS students.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at E.S.I.C. Medical College and Hospital (E.S.I.C.M.C.H.), Bihta, Patna.

Participants: First-year MBBS students enrolled in the academic year at E.S.I.C.M.C.H., Bihta, Patna, were selected for the study. A total of 130 first year students of two academic sessions were divided equally into two groups of 65 each.

Inclusion Criteria:

- First-year MBBS students willing to participate.
- Regular attendance in lectures (at least 75% attendance).

Exclusion Criteria:

- Students with prior knowledge or exposure to the subjects being taught.
- Students with less than 75% attendance in the lectures.

Bias: To minimize bias, students were randomly assigned to either the flipped classroom group or the traditional lecture group. Both groups covered the same curriculum and were assessed using the same evaluation tools.

Variables:

- Independent Variable: Type of classroom (flipped vs. traditional).
- Dependent Variables: Students' academic performance (exam scores), student engagement, and feedback on learning experience.

Data Collection: Data were collected through pre-tests and post-tests administered to both groups before and after the intervention. Additionally, feedback questionnaires were distributed to gather students' perceptions and experiences regarding the teaching methods.

Procedure:

1. Traditional Lecture Group:

- Attended conventional lectures where the instructor delivered content directly in the classroom.
- Students took notes and were encouraged to ask questions at the end of the lecture.

2. Flipped Classroom Group:

- Received pre-recorded video lectures and reading materials prior to the class.
- In-class time was devoted to interactive activities such as quizzes, group discussions, and problem-solving exercises to apply the concepts learned.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of

E.S.I.C.M.C.H., Bihta, Patna. Informed consent was obtained from all participants

Results

Participant Demographics: A total of 130 first-year MBBS students of two academic sessions participated in the study, with 65 students in each group. The demographic characteristics of the participants were comparable across both groups,

ensuring that there was no significant difference that could bias the results.

Academic Performance

Pre-Test Scores: Both groups took a pre-test to assess their baseline knowledge. The mean pre-test scores were similar, indicating no significant difference between the groups at the start of the study.

Group	Mean Pre-Test Score	Standard Deviation
Traditional Lecture Group	56.3	8.4
Flipped Classroom Group	57.1	8.1
p-value	0.532	-

Post-Test Scores: After 10 months of intervention, both groups were evaluated through a post-test.

Group	Mean Post-Test Score	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference
Traditional Lecture Group	68.4	7.9	12.1
Flipped Classroom Group	75.6	7.3	18.5

Improvement Scores: The improvement in scores from pre-test to post-test was analyzed.

Group	Mean Improvement	Standard Deviation
Traditional Lecture Group	12.1	6.5
Flipped Classroom Group	18.5	7.1

Student Engagement and Feedback: Feedback from students was collected to assess their engagement and satisfaction with the teaching methods. The feedback was measured using a Likert scale from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates "strongly disagree" and 5 indicates "strongly agree."

Feedback Question	Traditional Lecture Group (Mean ± SD)	Flipped Classroom Group (Mean ± SD)	p-value
The teaching method helped me understand the material.	3.8 ± 0.9	4.4 ± 0.7	0.002
I felt more engaged during the class sessions.	3.2 ± 1.0	4.6 ± 0.6	<0.001
I found the class sessions enjoyable and stimulating.	3.5 ± 0.8	4.3 ± 0.7	0.004
I am satisfied with the overall learning experience.	3.7 ± 0.9	4.5 ± 0.7	0.001

The study's findings demonstrate that the flipped classroom method outperformed the traditional lecture approach in enhancing academic performance for first-year MBBS students. Students in the flipped classroom group achieved notably higher mean post-test scores compared to those in the traditional lecture group (75.6 vs. 68.4, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, the increase in scores from pre-test to post-test was significantly larger in the flipped classroom group (18.5 vs. 12.1, $p < 0.001$).

Feedback from students further supports these findings, with the flipped classroom group reporting higher levels of engagement, understanding, enjoyment, and overall satisfaction. These differences were statistically significant, with p-values well below 0.05 for all feedback questions.

Discussion

The comparative study among flipped classroom-assisted lectures and traditional lecture classes among first-year MBBS students at E.S.I.C.M.C.H., Bihta, Patna, reveals significant findings that align with current research in medical education.

Academic Performance

The study found that students in the flipped classroom group significantly outperformed those in the traditional lecture group in post-test scores. The mean post-test scores for the flipped classroom group were 75.6 compared to 68.4 for the traditional lecture group, with a p-value of <0.001 . This improvement was supported by a noteworthy increase in the mean improvement scores from pre-

test to post-test, with the flipped classroom group showing an 18.5-point increase compared to 12.1 points in the traditional group ($p < 0.001$).

These findings are consistent with several studies. For instance, Hu et al. (2019) found that medical undergraduates in the flipped classroom group had significantly higher scores in exams and better self-reported learning outcomes compared to those in the traditional lecture group [5]. Similarly, Bansal et al. (2020) reported a 13% improvement in exam scores for medical students using the flipped classroom approach, particularly among lower-performing students [6].

Student Engagement and Satisfaction: Feedback from students indicated higher engagement, understanding, enjoyment, and overall satisfaction with the flipped classroom method. This was observed in the significantly higher scores for engagement (4.6 vs. 3.2), enjoyment (4.3 vs. 3.5), and overall satisfaction (4.5 vs. 3.7) with p -values < 0.01 .

This aligns with findings from Jafferjee et al. (2021), where students who engaged in the flipped classroom model reported higher satisfaction and perceived learning gains despite no significant differences in overall learning outcomes [7]. Another meta-analysis by Gillette et al. (2018) also found that while the flipped classroom may offer minimal gains in knowledge, it significantly enhances student satisfaction and engagement [8].

Implications for Medical Education: The flipped classroom model's effectiveness in improving student performance and satisfaction highlights its potential in medical education. By engaging students in active learning and application of knowledge during class time, the flipped classroom addresses the limitations of passive learning associated with traditional lectures. Chen et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of integrating pre-class learning with in-class activities to enhance cognitive learning [9]. Additionally, Dehghanzadeh and Jafaraghaee (2018) demonstrated that the flipped classroom significantly improved critical thinking dispositions among nursing students [10].

Challenges and Considerations: Despite the positive outcomes, the employment of flipped classroom model requires significant resources, including time for preparing pre-class materials as well as facilitating in-class events. Faculty training and technological infrastructure are essential to support this model effectively. Smith et al. (2020) noted that while student sentiments were more positive towards the flipped classroom, the preparation required for faculty was substantial [11].

Furthermore, a systematic review by Evans et al. (2019) highlighted that while the flipped classroom can improve engagement and satisfaction, its im-

pact on learning outcomes is variable and may not always be significant [12].

Conclusion

The flipped classroom model has demonstrated significant improvements in academic performance, student engagement, and satisfaction among first-year MBBS students. These findings suggest that medical colleges should consider integrating flipped classroom approaches to foster better learning outcomes and student experiences. However, the implementation requires careful planning, adequate resources, and continuous evaluation to address potential challenges and maximize its benefits.

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